

Fencing Hallucination - Increasing Artistic Control in Interactive Media Arts by Merging AI Models with Hand-coded Programs

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Figure 1: Two chronophotographs across 134 years. (A) A chronophotograph created in 1880 by Etienne-Jules Marey, documenting a fencing lunge. (B) A chronophotograph synthesized by AI from real-time human-AI fencing interaction in Fencing Hallucination.

ABSTRACT

The rise of diffusion models in AI image synthesis revolutionized computational image generation, challenging the traditional notion of photographic objectivity. This advancement posed a dual challenge for media artists: to harness AI's potential while preserving artistic uniqueness. In *Fencing Hallucination*, we explored integrating AI models into a traditional hand-coded computation pipeline, introducing real-time interactivity to AI image synthesis and increasing the artistic control of the AI-generated images. The research culminated in an interactive installation exhibited at various venues, attracting over 800 audience visits. The system generated authentic chronophotographs from diverse human-AI interactions while maintaining consistent aesthetic control. This project exemplifies the potential of combining AI models and hand-coded programs, which pave the way to better human-AI co-creative systems.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Applied computing → Media arts; • Human-centered computing → Gestural input.

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, Generative Art, Generative AI, Interactive Art Installation, Human-computer Interaction

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1 INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, each new image-creation tool has seen experiments that diverge from its original purpose, producing surprising images. These innovative ideas reshape visual traditions and culture, establishing aesthetic norms. The birth of photography witnessed creative uses like chronophotograph[Marey and Fremont 1894] and photogram[Ray 1928], which were quickly followed by the invention of motion pictures[Muybridge 1879] and special effects[Méliès 1900], and experimental abstract films[McLaren 1968] introduced unprecedented effects.

In the 1960s, artists began using computers as new image-making tools, generating complex geometries and rule-based artwork through

Figure 2: Generation process of an example chronophotograph. The computation is carried out in four steps (from top to bottom): human skeleton tracking by Kinect, opponent pose generation by AI, pose-to-image translation, and blending image into final chronophotograph. The audience triggers the system to record their pose into the final image when they move energetically. They can trigger multiple times (4 times in this example) during their interactive experience, resulting in the complex details in the final image.

random and procedural algorithms. Sensory technology advancements produce large amounts of data, giving birth to data art. In data art, the human body is no longer abstracted by custom or special lighting but by computer vision and by extracting skeletal data for geometric or avatar-like presentations[Gremmler 2016; Quayola and Akten 2011]. Recently, AI has emerged as the latest image-creation technology, with text-to-image[Rombach et al. 2022] and text-to-video tools[OpenAI 2024] gaining unprecedented popularity. Unlike earlier AI tools demanding high technology proficiency since 2015, today’s AI tools are accessible to everyone due to their ease of use. Anyone can generate realistic images or short videos with just a text description. However, on the other hand, the lack of artistic control other than text prompts makes these tools challenging for artists to be innovative and create unique results.

Those who have followed AI-generated imagery from the era of DeepDream[Mordvintsev et al. 2015] would have encountered various experimental and unconventional methods of using AI tools compared to the current mainstream text-prompting approach. Techniques such as utilizing custom dataset[Ridler 2018], exploring the latent space[Anadol 2019], and visualizing the latent space through dimensionality reduction are some examples. However, the present ecosystem, flooded with ordinary users lacking aesthetic or technical training, primarily uses text-to-image tools to generate

images[Wilde 2023]. This has turned into a competition of who can craft better prompts to create more surreal images. While it’s undeniable that this method is not trivial and can produce some remarkable images, its popularity largely discourages more diverse usage methods. It unnecessarily necessitates the understanding of the underlying principles of AI generation, thereby inhibiting the modification of AI tools by integrating traditional visual creation experiences. As a result, artworks produced this way often lack depth and exhibit homogenization. Artists find themselves in a dilemma: by choosing to use AI, they have to exercise their creative agency at a compromise, making it challenging to produce fundamentally different works from those of other users.

AI as of today cannot truly innovate; it merely generates images similar to those in its training set. Based on this understanding, *Fencing Hallucination* strategically conceptualized AI image synthesis as purely an image-rendering tool, stripping it of its innovative agency. This strategy opened the door to integrating AI into a hand-coded programming pipeline to create familiar art forms such as interactive art and abstract photography. In this way, the result builds upon and extends past visual arts tradition. This approach received positive responses in exhibitions and fostered audience understanding of AI, including the model training and fine-tuning efforts behind achieving these effects. It can inspire more people

to experiment with AI technology, exercising true artistic control rather than surrendering their creative agency to AI in hopes of being surprised.

This project, by intentionally using AI to recreate traditional styles, demonstrates the potential of improving artistic control in AI image synthesis. It encourages further exploration in this direction, ultimately generating works with a more distinct authorial style.

2 RELATED WORKS

2.1 Artistic Control in AI Image Synthesis

The development of AI image synthesis began with the introduction of DeepDream[Mordvintsev et al. 2015] in 2015, sparking significant interest in AI-generated imagery among visual artists. This interest was soon followed by the widespread adoption of Style Transfer[Gatys et al. 2016] and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)[Goodfellow et al. 2014; Karras et al. 2019; Radford et al. 2015]. These technologies have markedly improved the quality, diversity, and accessibility of AI-generated images, culminating in the latest breakthroughs with diffusion models[Rombach et al. 2022] and text-to-image generators.

Despite these advancements, fundamental challenges persist: AI inherently tends to 1) mimic its training data and 2) operate as a "black box" that produces outputs in a single step. These AI imaging tool characteristics starkly contrast the iterative, exploratory process that artists typically employ to develop their style and refine their work. While a few artists have successfully navigated these limitations by using entirely original datasets [Ridler 2018] or by developing novel AI workflows [White 2019], the majority of AI-based art images remain heavily reliant on the results generated by the AI[Akten 2018; Anadol 2019; Klingemann 2018]. This reliance often leads to a homogenization of artistic outputs due to the insufficient artistic controls available to the artist.

These issues are further exacerbated in text-to-image generators, which tend to produce even greater homogenization. Users can generate complex, super photorealistic yet aesthetically pleasing images by simply entering text descriptions of the desired outcome. The unnecessary of engaging with the underlying workings of the model discourage the exploration of more diverse control methods. Additionally, since these models are trained to align the generated image by treating the text prompt as descriptions, they often struggle with abstract concepts, thus making the text input alone insufficient for users to exercise complete artistic control over the visual style of the images produced. Furthermore, the expressive power of a single image is inherently limited, a constraint amplified by the lack of the tangible presence found in traditional photographs.

To address these limitations, the project *Fencing Hallucination* first explored artistic controls beyond text prompts — using human skeletal movement as the input to guide image generation. The artistic control over the outcome visual style was further implemented by delving into the model's internal workings and employing fine-tuning techniques to control the model's generative style, ensuring the consistency across generated images. This approach enables the resurrection of the visual style created by Marey[Marey and Fremont 1894] and McLaren[McLaren 1968] in the age of AI and results in striking AI-generated chronophotographs. On the other hand, the project aims to encourage AI-based visual artists to renew

traditional image computation methods with emerging AI tools to produce AI imagery that extends previous visual art culture.

Notably, while AI text-to-video generators are advancing rapidly and can produce sequences of frames for synthesizing chronophotographs, they still lack the interactivity of "Fencing Hallucination." The success of this project lies in its ability to engage viewers, offering a unique interactive experience that static visual output cannot match.

2.2 Interactive Visual Art

Interactive art enables the dynamic modification of an artwork's outcome through the physical interaction or engagement of the viewer. This art form typically involves sensing the audience's actions, such as bodily movements[Krueger 1975; Rozin 1999; Tokyo 2016], gestures[Rokeby 1986], brainwaves[Samanci and Caniglia 2018], and other physiological signals[Han and Surve 2019], and translating these inputs into visual or auditory feedback. This real-time interaction distinctly sets interactive art apart from other art forms.

Interactive art can be seen in certain video games, where player actions directly impact the game environment and outcomes, providing an immersive and responsive experience. The key difference lies in the objective: video games are designed to entertain, often using scoring systems to motivate player engagement, whereas interactive art emphasizes the design of the interactive experience to convey the artist's message to the participant.

Some artworks utilize similar data sources and convert this data offline into sculptures[Jansen 2006; Zhang et al. 2018] or videos[Gremmler 2016; Quayola and Akten 2011]. While these pieces are innovative and inspiring, they do not fall into the scope of interactive art, as the transformation and feedback do not occur instantaneously, thus lacking the immediate and dynamic response characteristic of interactive art.

With advancements in computer technology and sensors, coupled with the evolution of modern art, interactive art has become increasingly prevalent, often implemented with rule-based, procedural algorithmic processing of interactive data in generating its result. However, examples of real-time interactive art employing AI technology[Akten et al. 2019; Zhang and Ren 2021] are relatively rare. One reason for this scarcity is the inflexibility in re-purposing a trained model. A model is trained to perform a specialized task that defined in its training dataset. As Interactive art necessitates a mapping between interactive behaviors and visual outcomes, the AI model for Interactive art would require to create a sufficiently large dataset of input-data-output-visual pairs. Additionally, AI models are often too computationally expensive to run real-time interaction.

Recent advancements have made it possible to control images using skeletal data[Zhang et al. 2023], addressing the issue of mapping interactive actions to visual effects. This allows different diffusion models to interact with body movements without the need for retraining. Furthermore, optimization on diffusion models has reduced computational requirements to enable real-time interaction [Kodaira et al. 2023].

Fencing Hallucination explored a novel form of interactive visual art. It resembled a sport game where an AI-trained fencing opponent interacts with the user. Unlike a game with scoring system, it was designed to encourage the audience to alter the generated images through interaction. Interestingly, the project did not aim to create a perfect AI. Instead, it used a limited amount of paired skeletal data collected from fencing videos to train a functional AI. As a result, the AI opponent did not appear as omnipotent as the stereotypical AI, encouraging viewers to question their beliefs about AI. Moreover, this project sought to show viewers about the characteristics and limitations of AI, highlighting the homogenization in an AI model's outputs. Like all interactive visual artworks, *Fencing Hallucination* provided a level of engagement that non-interactive visual works lack. The unique, user-generated images built deeper connections between the viewers and the artworks than other non-interactive AI-generated works. Viewers see themselves reflected in the artwork, enhancing their emotional engagement.

However, in the contemporary AI era, the scope of such diverse production has shrunk. Aside from a minority of projects that fine-tune AI models with custom datasets, the bulk of AI-based art now typically showcases the outputs from AI models with minimal alterations [Akten 2018; Anadol 2019; Klingemann 2018]. The root cause of this homogenization in both the artistic presentation and the technological approach lies in the fundamental differences between AI and traditional hand-coded programming; the latter allows for more direct and predictable code-level modifications, whereas AI tools demand change at the level of datasets and models to achieve unique outputs. However, compiling a sufficiently large and tailored dataset for effectual AI training is technically challenging and under-explored for media art practitioners. Additionally, the complexity and obscurity of adjusting AI model parameters further hinder artists' ability to experiment creatively with these models. Moreover, despite their powerful capabilities, the algorithms of AI models, particularly neural networks, are often too obscure to be transparently presented to audiences, leading to a disconnection between the creators and the final produced artifacts.

Therefore, to bring back the expressiveness characteristic of pre-AI-boom media art, we seek to strategically integrate generative AI within programmable new media workflows. Instead of using AI to handle the entire media computation workflow, we use the generative AI models only in specific media-transforming modules within the computational media pipeline. This hybrid approach diverges from typical AI tool applications of minimal customization by artists, empowering media artists to develop more diverse and expressive artistic forms.

In *Fencing Hallucination*, we put idea into practice by integrating two AI models into a hand-coded computational process for interactive art. The project culminated in a multi-screen interactive installation that provides the audience with a real-time, embodied human-AI interaction. Here, participants engage in a fencing game with an AI agent, their movements captured and interpreted by the AI to create a Chronophotograph unique to their interaction. This year-long exploration involves dataset development, model training, data visualization, creative expression with a hybrid of hand-code and AI models, and interactive experience design. This hybrid approach goes beyond mere dataset and model manipulation in an AI-centric approach, offering a broader range of artistic

Figure 3: Given a human skeleton captured from Kinect in real-time, an AI skeleton is generated by the Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) Neural Network trained on the dataset of skeleton pairs extracted from Fencing game videos.

controls for more nuanced creative expression, resulting in a better human-AI co-creative system [Rezwana and Maher 2023].

3 METHODS

The project started with collecting fencing game videos, serving as training materials to acquaint AI with the nuances of fencing. This dataset trained the models to generate skeletons responding to human gestures in real time. With the help of the diffusion model, the system then translated the pair of skeletons into a photorealistic image. With multiple pose-translated images generated by the diffusion model, the system employed a digitally simulated multi-exposure process to combine these pictures into a single final chronophotograph, paying tribute to the aesthetics of the Chronophotograph.

3.1 Real-time Human-AI Interactive Program

3.1.1 Training Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) to Predict Opponent Pose. We used a Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP), a type of Neural Network, to predict an opponent pose based on the input pose. Training this model requires the dataset of pairs of fencing poses from the two fencing players. Given the limited options and quality of the existing fencing motion capture dataset, we developed a new dataset from online fencing game videos with off-the-shelf AI-based pose estimation programs [Bajpai and Joshi 2021; Cao et al. 2017; Lugaresi et al. 2019]. The resulting dataset consists of 465 game round videos, ranging from 2 seconds to 30 seconds, and the two player's skeletal data in every frame of the 24-fps videos. We also extracted ten neighbor frames near the scoring moment in each video as a total of 4650 frames of two-player pose pairs to guide the model to focus more on the scoring lunge move and response.

3.1.2 Real-time Skeleton Tracking and Generation. Leveraging the model's rapid pose prediction capabilities, we developed an interactive program that uses real-time captured audience poses as model input. As the audience moves, their body poses are captured and

Figure 4: Pose-to-image translation with Stable Diffusion. The two control challenges, pose control and style control, are handled by ControlNet plug-in via its skeleton control and DreamBooth fine-tuning model weights with selected 9 images in the target style.

fed into the AI model, which generates an opposing pose. By visualizing the human and AI poses as avatars on a screen, the program affords the audience a real-time, embodied interaction with the AI. See fig.3.

3.2 Chronophotograph Synthesis

The advent of diffusion models enabled the system to create photorealistic images controlled by human poses. With the digital simulation of multi-exposure techniques, the system combines multiple images as one final chronophotograph image. See fig.4.

3.2.1 Pose-to-Image Translation with Stable Diffusion. Stable Diffusion can perform the image-to-image task to translate an image into another based on the text prompt's content, in our case, the fencing game scene. However, two challenges must be overcome before we can use them in our pipeline. First, even if the model can generate an image of two fencers based on our description in the text prompt, the fencers' pose may not match our human-AI skeleton pairs, failing bodily interactive control on image content. To tackle this challenge, we used the ControlNet plug-in to enable the model to take a skeletal image in openpose format as a form of control on the output, ensuring the pose consistency between the input image and the result.

Second, off-the-shelf Stable Diffusion cannot maintain the same visual appearance across different images. Even using the same text prompt and seed, the slight change in the input image results in dramatic changes in the result, breaking the visual continuity between the two images. This inconsistency makes it difficult to perform the following blending operation seamlessly. To keep the style of a clean shot of the fencing players against the black background, we collected nine images with our desired visual style as the dataset to fine-tune the model weights. Eventually, our model produces the same visual style images with changing input images or text prompts.

3.2.2 Simulated Multi-exposure with Image Blending. The original chronophotograph uses a multi-exposure process that opens the shutter multiple times to record different moments in the same photograph. Similarly, in Fencing Hallucination, we emulate the process by generating photographs of humans and AI at different moments and blending them into one image. To blend the images, we modified the standard "add" blending with 0.95 intensity decay for every layer so that the temporal information can be encoded into the varying intensity: the darker the earlier, and the brighter the later. The blending equation is defined as: $a' = 1 - (1 - a * 0.95) * (1 - b)$ in which a is the current chronophotograph, b is the new layer to be overlaid on the top, and a' is the result after blending them.

4 INSTALLATION AND EXHIBITION

By integrating the interactive program and the chronophotograph synthesis module, this project results in a multi-screen installation that offers a unique experience of human-AI real-time interaction, manifesting in a collaboratively created chronophotograph. Refer to fig.5. The system consists of a computer (i7-13700 CPU, 2080Ti GPU, 32GB RAM), a Kinect V2 motion capture sensor, two large display set back-to-back, and a camera flash controlled by the computer program via a customized circuit. The interactive program of "Fencing Hallucination" has been showcased at two venues (see fig.5 A & B), captivating over 800 viewers and producing diverse chronophotographs as results (results in fig.5 C).

We crafted a user experience so intuitively accessible that the interaction requires no technical expertise. Participants engage with the system simply by moving in front of a screen. This action prompts the immediate display of two responsive avatars representing the participant and an AI fencer (2, second row). Behind the scenes, the system synthesizes pose-guided images, merges them into the current chronophotograph, and shows them on the screen. As the chronophotograph updates with new layers (2 fourth row), the intermediate results are constantly uploaded to the cloud server until the generation process is finished. A QR code of the image download link from the server is created and displayed at the screen's corner for the participants' access to their unique chronophotographs. Furthermore, our design integrates an element reminiscent of an on-ride camera experience by featuring a camera flash activated at moments when the audience moves energetically during the experience and printing on photographs the time and location of the interaction, augmenting the playfulness and deepening the level of immersion within the experience.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel method of incorporating AI image generators into hand-coded workflows to enhance artistic control. By strategically using AI modules as stable modules responsible for specific computations, users can design entire workflows to achieve desired artistic control, such as interaction design, style control, and the rule of image generation, which in our case are the real-time bodily interaction, in fencing photorealistic style, and the form of chronophotography. This approach addresses the over-reliance on AI-generated results and the homogeneity issue due to a lack of personalized control. The paper demonstrates this method through

Figure 5: People interacting with Fencing Hallucination during exhibitions (A&B) and selected results from audiences (C), exhibiting a balance of consistency and diversity in the visual style of generated images.

the Fencing Hallucination project, which integrates AI and hand-coded programming to create an interactive art installation where users engage in a fencing game with a virtual AI opponent. The system generates style-consistent images using a diffusion model to simulate the process of chronophotography. This installation not only showcases the potential of AI in artistic control but also encourages participants to reflect on the nature and limitations of AI, thus fostering a deeper understanding and innovative use of AI in creative visual culture. However, the project has some notable limitations that will be addressed in future work:

Lack of Visual Novelty: Fencing Hallucination pays homage to style in chronophotography, which is novel within the realm of AI-generated images. However, it may need more exploration of visual novelty through the lens of visual art in general. Beyond the visual novelty, this project aims to encourage more visual artists to bring past artistic experiences into the application of AI image synthesis, using this method as a new exploratory direction to enrich the ecosystem of human-AI co-creation.

High Technical Proficiency Required: The method proposed in this paper does not eliminate the technical demands of AI tools. Instead, it requires creators to have a certain level of technical proficiency to connect different computational modules. It is acceptable to require a certain level of technical proficiency because each original artistic creation is highly customized, and tool development is usually a necessary part of the creative process. Despite this, this project's data collection tools and model fine-tuning tools are highly applicable to similar scenarios. We will develop simplified tools to enable more people to share our workflow.

We hope these improvements will further promote understanding and practical application of AI in artistic creation.

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